
Funding: University of York, 2023.

**Funding: The University of Pristina,
Pristina, Kosovo.**

**Editorial: Al Najah National University
Ivan Nikolic, Ph.D. Author. May 2023.**

////////423928738923//////////53276489322

//////////4372492467893762////////23//22/

The Role of NATO in Serbia-Kosovo Crisis, 826 C.E. - 2023

What is the West specifically invested in?

The North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) has historically played a significant role in maintaining stability and peace in the Balkans. However, the tensions and disputes between Serbia and Kosovo persistently present challenges to regional stability. This article explores the critical role NATO could play in diffusing the Serbia-Kosovo crisis and facilitating a sustainable resolution. It also introduces a tertiary model in which an intersection of race as a social construct drives the support from the West toward populations who share the same racialization construct with those in the West.

The history of the Serbia-Kosovo region is characterized by cultural intermingling, political upheavals, and conflicts that date back to the Middle Ages. The earliest references to the region denote a rich tapestry of tribal and later feudal domains, culminating in the establishment of powerful Serbian states.

Onset to 14th Century

From the 8th to the 14th century, the region was a theatre of fluctuating boundaries between the Byzantine Empire and the Bulgarian Empire, with the Serbs gradually establishing control over Kosovo (Sedlar, 1994). The region was incorporated into the medieval Serbian state under the Nemanjić

dynasty in the 13th century (Ćirković, 2004).

The Battle of Kosovo in 1389 is a significant event. Despite ending in a stalemate, it symbolized the beginning of the end of Serbian power in the region, as the Ottoman Empire expanded its territories (Emmert, 1990). Following the battle, the Ottoman Empire gradually took control of the region, culminating in full occupation by the mid-15th century (Sicker, 2001).

Under the Ottoman rule, a significant portion of the Serbian population migrated northwards, while many who stayed converted to Islam. Simultaneously, the Albanian population gradually increased in the region, becoming a majority by the late 17th century (Malcolm, 1998).

The 19th century saw a resurgence of Serbian national identity, fueled by romantic nationalism. The 1878 Congress of Berlin recognized Serbia as an independent state but left Kosovo within the Ottoman Empire, triggering dissatisfaction among Serbian nationalists (Jelavich, 1983).

The Balkan Wars (1912-1913) resulted in the region coming under Serbian control once more. However, during World War II, Kosovo was incorporated into Italian-controlled Albania. The post-war communist regime of Yugoslavia under Josip Broz Tito made Kosovo an autonomous region of Serbia in 1946 and further upgraded its status to an autonomous province in 1963 (Pavlowitch, 2002).

In the late 1980s, rising nationalism, led by Serbian leader Slobodan Milosevic, resulted in the revocation of Kosovo's autonomy, leading to increased tensions and clashes between the Serbian authorities and the

Kosovar Albanians, setting the stage for the 1990s conflict (Judah, 2002).

Religious Migration: Christian Orthodoxy to Islam

Understanding the religious transformation of Kosovo's population from Orthodox Christianity to Islam requires delving into a complex historical narrative marked by sociopolitical changes and external influences.

Between the 8th and the 14th centuries, the area that is now Kosovo was primarily inhabited by Orthodox Christian Serbs, under the rule of the Serbian medieval state and the Eastern Orthodox Church (Ćirković, 2004). However, the Battle of Kosovo in 1389 marked a turning point, with the Ottoman Empire gradually extending its control over the region.

Following their complete takeover by the mid-15th century, the Ottomans embarked on a policy of Islamization, which wasn't an instantaneous process but spanned centuries (Inalcik, 1973). This Islamization was not achieved primarily through force but rather through incentives. The Ottoman system favored Muslims in terms of taxes and civil service opportunities, offering non-Muslim subjects a significant incentive to convert to Islam (Sicker, 2001).

The Orthodox Christian clergy and nobility often had their properties seized by the Ottomans, leading many to convert to retain their status and wealth (Malcolm, 1998). Additionally, many Serbs migrated northwards to escape the Ottoman rule, further changing the demographic landscape of Kosovo (Sicker, 2001).

The spread of Islam was also facilitated by the Sufi orders, Islamic mystic fraternities,

which played a significant role in the Islamization of Albanians in Kosovo (Endresen, 2011). They offered a form of Islam that retained many Christian and pagan practices, making it more palatable to converts (Endresen, 2011).

By the late 17th century, the Albanian population, most of whom had converted to Islam, became a majority in the region (Malcolm, 1998). This situation was further amplified by the mass migration of Orthodox Christian Serbs during the Great Serb Migration of 1690 following the failed Vienna War (Pavlowitch, 2002).

The conversion of Kosovars from Greek Orthodox Christianity to Islam was a complex process influenced by socio-political and economic factors during the Ottoman rule. It was an extensive process that significantly shaped the cultural, religious, and ethnic fabric of modern-day Kosovo.

Religious Conversion: Impelled or Compelled Social Construct

The conversion of the population in Kosovo from Christianity to Islam is a multifaceted process that unfolded over centuries under Ottoman rule. The narrative of forced conversions to Islam is overly simplistic and doesn't fully capture the nuances of this historical phenomenon.

Following the Battle of Kosovo in 1389, the Ottoman Empire gradually seized control of the region. The Ottomans generally adhered to a policy of religious tolerance, where the non-Muslim population, or dhimmis, were granted certain protections and rights, including the freedom to practice their religion, in exchange for the payment of the jizya tax (Inalcik, 1973). Therefore, while the Ottomans did not impose a policy of

forced conversions, their rule came with a systemic favoring of Islam.

The notion of systemic favoring refers to a series of incentives for conversion to Islam. For instance, Muslims were exempted from the *jizya* tax, had more legal rights, and had better opportunities for social advancement within the Ottoman system (Inalcik, 1973). Thus, conversion was often a pragmatic decision taken for socio-economic reasons rather than a result of direct coercion (Malcolm, 1998).

However, this does not mean that the process was entirely voluntary or peaceful. The *devshirme* system, whereby Christian boys were taken by the Ottomans to serve in the military or administrative apparatus, resulted in compulsory conversion to Islam (Sicker, 2001). Moreover, the properties of the Orthodox Christian clergy and nobility were often seized, incentivizing many to convert to retain their status and wealth (Malcolm, 1998).

The role of Sufi orders in the conversion process is also significant. They presented a form of Islam that incorporated many Christian and pagan elements, which eased the transition for many converts (Endresen, 2011). Their influence was particularly strong among the Albanians in Kosovo.

By the late 17th century, the majority of the population in Kosovo were Albanians, who were largely Muslim. The Great Serb Migration of 1690, where many Serbs fled northwards following the failed Vienna War, also contributed to this demographic shift (Pavlowitch, 2002).

While there was no policy of forced conversions by the Ottoman Empire, the socio-political climate and systemic favoring

of Islam led many in Kosovo to convert over time, for a complex blend of reasons.

The 20th Century Disputes

The Serbia-Kosovo dispute roots back to the 1990s, when Kosovo declared independence from Serbia following years of conflicts, including the devastating Kosovo War (1998-1999). Despite Kosovo's unilateral declaration of independence in 2008, Serbia continues to deny its sovereignty (Judah, 2008). The ensuing Serbia-Kosovo crisis has been characterized by political tensions, ethnic clashes, and economic disparities (Ker-Lindsay, 2019).

NATO has been involved in the region since the 1990s, particularly during the Kosovo War when it launched a 78-day airstrike campaign against Yugoslavia (Serbia and Montenegro) to halt the mass expulsion and ethnic cleansing of Kosovar Albanians (Daalder & O'Hanlon, 2000). Since then, NATO has maintained a peacekeeping presence in Kosovo through the NATO-led Kosovo Force (KFOR) to ensure a safe and secure environment (NATO, 2021).

NATO's current role is crucial as it maintains stability and discourages any aggressive actions from both sides. With a well-established reputation as a peacekeeping force, it holds a unique position to facilitate dialogue and negotiations between Serbia and Kosovo. In fact, it has already been indirectly involved in fostering political dialogue through the European Union-facilitated Brussels Dialogue, which began in 2013 (Emini & Reljic, 2017).

However, NATO's role could be more proactive. To address the Serbia-Kosovo crisis effectively, NATO could extend its remit beyond its current peacekeeping

function. First, NATO could play a more assertive role in facilitating diplomatic negotiations. Although this is traditionally a role for the United Nations or the European Union, NATO's strategic interest in the region, combined with its history and presence, position it as a credible intermediary (Bieber, 2015).

Second, NATO could assist in reforming the security structures in both Serbia and Kosovo. Kosovo's security force is still maturing and seeks to transform into a full-fledged army, a move that Serbia vehemently opposes (BBC, 2018). NATO could provide oversight and capacity-building, ensuring that any changes in security structures are conducted responsibly, transparently, and with due respect for regional stability (Dempsey, 2019).

Third, NATO could aid in tackling the socio-economic factors that underpin the Serbia-Kosovo crisis. By promoting social inclusion, economic development, and reconciliation, NATO could contribute to creating an environment conducive to peace and stability (Caparini & Koser, 2017).

NATO's broader involvement in the Serbia-Kosovo crisis is not without challenges. Russia, a traditional ally of Serbia, is wary of NATO's expansion in the region (Webber, 2019). Moreover, NATO must tread carefully to avoid perceptions of bias, given its history during the Kosovo War. Nevertheless, these challenges underscore the need for NATO to act cautiously, transparently, and in collaboration with other international actors such as the European Union and the United Nations.

While the Serbia-Kosovo crisis remains a significant challenge to regional stability in the Balkans, it also presents an opportunity

for NATO to demonstrate its capacity to manage and resolve complex conflicts. By playing a more proactive role, NATO could contribute significantly to a sustainable resolution between Serbia and Kosovo, thus ensuring long-term stability in the region.

Ask the Right Question: Why do Serbs Despise Kosovars?

Framing any discussion on the tension between Serbs and Kosovo Albanians (who are predominantly Muslim) around the concept of 'hate' is overly simplistic. The historical, political, and sociocultural factors that have shaped relations between these communities are complex and multi-faceted. Nevertheless, understanding the underlying sources of tension can help provide a more nuanced perspective.

One significant source of discord dates back to the Battle of Kosovo in 1389, an event deeply ingrained in Serbian national mythology as a symbol of heroic self-sacrifice against the invading Ottoman Turks (Emmert, 1990). This historical event, although centuries old, has been perpetuated in Serbian consciousness as a narrative of martyrdom and loss of their ancestral homeland.

During the Ottoman rule, the demographic balance shifted, as many Serbs migrated northwards, while the Albanian population (majority of whom converted to Islam) increased (Malcolm, 1998). Serbs often associate this period with forced displacement and Islamization, further ingraining resentment (Fine, 1994).

The tension was aggravated in the 20th century under Josip Broz Tito's Communist regime, which granted Kosovo the status of an autonomous province within Serbia. Many Serbs perceived this as favoritism

towards the Albanian majority in Kosovo (Pavlowitch, 2002).

The conflict of the 1990s, marked by brutal violence and human rights abuses from both sides, significantly worsened the relationship. The systematic persecution of Albanians by Serbian forces under Slobodan Milosevic's regime, followed by the retaliatory violence against Serbs after the NATO intervention, deepened the mutual mistrust and animosity (Judah, 2002).

The declaration of independence by Kosovo in 2008, which Serbia vehemently opposes, has only added fuel to the fire. Serbia, backed by its powerful ally Russia, insists that Kosovo remains an integral part of its territory (Perritt, 2008).

The Serbian Orthodox Church's stance, considering Kosovo the cradle of Serbian Orthodoxy, further deepens the resentment towards Kosovo's predominantly Muslim population (Gallagher, 2005).

Therefore, the strained relationship between Serbs and Kosovo Albanians is less about religious hatred and more about a complex interplay of historical grievances, national identity, territorial claims, and political power struggles.

Serbian Aggression Analogues of Bosnia and Kosovo-

The conflicts in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Kosovo during the 1990s share several similarities due to the shared historical backdrop of the dissolution of Yugoslavia. Yet, they also present distinct characteristics given their specific socio-political contexts.

In both conflicts, the Serbs' main objective was to create ethnically homogenous territories. In Bosnia, this resulted in the

systematic ethnic cleansing of Bosniak Muslims, culminating in the Srebrenica genocide in 1995 (Bougarel, Helms, & Duijzings, 2007). Similarly, in Kosovo, the late 1990s saw a brutal campaign of repression and expulsion against Kosovo Albanians (who are predominantly Muslim), undertaken by the Serbian forces under Slobodan Milosevic's regime (Judah, 2002).

However, the scale and nature of the violence differed considerably. The war in Bosnia and Herzegovina was characterized by mass atrocities committed by all parties involved, albeit with the majority of the crimes attributed to the Bosnian Serb forces (Bassiouni, 1994). The Srebrenica massacre, recognized as genocide by international courts, was the most horrific episode, with approximately 8,000 Bosniak Muslim men and boys systematically killed by Bosnian Serb forces (United Nations, 1995).

In Kosovo, although the violence was also brutal, it did not culminate in an event comparable to Srebrenica—thanks to NATO, especially the United States, the UK and Canada. The Kosovo conflict was primarily characterized by a systematic campaign of repression, which included forced displacement, mass killings, and rape, aimed at expelling the Albanian population (Human Rights Watch, 2001). The death toll, while difficult to ascertain due to the nature of the conflict, is estimated to be around 10,000, the majority of whom were Kosovo Albanians (Ball, Betts, Scheuren, Dudukovich, & Asher, 2002).

The international community's response also varied. In Bosnia, despite the imposition of a UN peacekeeping mission, the UN was widely criticized for its failure to prevent the Srebrenica genocide (Power, 2002). On the other hand, in Kosovo, NATO intervened militarily in 1999 to halt Serbian aggression

(Independent International Commission on Kosovo, 2000). This marked a shift in international policy towards humanitarian intervention, influenced by the lessons learned from the Bosnian war.

The post-conflict trajectories of both regions have also diverged. Bosnia and Herzegovina, under the Dayton Agreement, has remained a single state, albeit divided into two entities. Despite this, ethnic tensions persist, and the reconciliation process has been slow (Toal, 2013). In contrast, Kosovo unilaterally declared independence from Serbia in 2008, a move recognized by many countries, although not by Serbia or Russia (Ker-Lindsay, 2009).

While both conflicts share a common backdrop of ethnic tensions and territorial disputes following the collapse of Yugoslavia, the nature and scale of violence, international responses, and post-conflict trajectories differ significantly.

Etic View on the Suppression of Muslims and the Intersection of Race, Tertiary Homologue of Palestine.

Bosnia and Herzegovina: During the Bosnian War (1992-1995), NATO's initial involvement was limited to enforcing a no-fly zone and carrying out limited airstrikes (Ripley, 1999). However, NATO's role expanded dramatically following the Srebrenica massacre in July 1995, where Bosnian Serb forces systematically killed around 8,000 Bosniak Muslims (United Nations, 1995). NATO's subsequent large-scale bombing campaign against Bosnian Serb forces, Operation Deliberate Force, was instrumental in bringing the parties to the negotiating table, leading to the Dayton Agreement in November 1995 (Ripley, 1999).

Post-conflict, NATO led the Implementation Force (IFOR) and Stabilization Force (SFOR) missions to maintain peace, oversee the military aspects of the Dayton Agreement, and protect all citizens, including Bosniak Muslims (Ripley, 1999).

Bosnian Muslims, officially recognized as "Bosniaks," are considered a South Slavic ethnic group. They primarily inhabit Bosnia and Herzegovina, with significant communities in Serbia, Montenegro, and Croatia (Donia & Fine, 1994).

The term Bosniak is relatively recent, emerging in the late 20th century to designate the Bosnian Muslims as a distinct ethnic group, separate from other South Slavic nations. Historically, Bosniaks shared a common Slavic ancestry with Serbs and Croats. The distinction began primarily in the late Middle Ages, when the region of Bosnia, previously Christian, came under the rule of the Ottoman Empire, and a significant portion of the population converted to Islam (Pinson, 1994).

Bosniak identity is thus more of a cultural and religious identifier than a racial one, although they are socially constructed into the racial groups as white (Pinson, 1994). The primary distinction between Bosniaks, Serbs, and Croats, who all share South Slavic ancestry, lies in their religious affiliations: Bosniaks are predominantly Muslim, while Serbs are Orthodox Christians and Croats are Roman Catholics (Bougarel, 2007).

Bosniaks, or Bosnian Muslims, are an ethnic group, predominantly of South Slavic origin, characterized by their historical adherence to Islam. This identity has emerged within the unique historical and cultural context of the Balkans.

Kosovo: NATO's role in Kosovo was more proactive. During the 1998-1999 Kosovo War, in response to a brutal campaign of repression and expulsion of Kosovo Albanians by Serbian forces, NATO intervened without UN Security Council authorization, citing a humanitarian emergency (Independent International Commission on Kosovo, 2000). The 78-day bombing campaign forced Serbia to withdraw its forces from Kosovo, effectively protecting the Kosovo Albanians, who are predominantly Muslim (Independent International Commission on Kosovo, 2000).

Since 1999, NATO has maintained a peacekeeping presence in Kosovo through the Kosovo Force (KFOR), with the mandate to ensure a safe and secure environment for all inhabitants (NATO, 2021).

Kosovo Muslims, or Kosovar Albanians, constitute the majority of the population in Kosovo and are predominantly of Albanian ethnicity. The ethno-national identity of Kosovo Albanians is complex, shaped by historical, cultural, and linguistic factors.

Historically, the region that is now Kosovo was inhabited by various ethnic groups, including Illyrians, Romans, Slavs, and others. Kosovar Albanians trace their ancestry to the ancient Illyrians, indigenous inhabitants of the Western Balkans, although this claim has been a subject of academic debate (Malcolm, 1998).

The major distinction emerged during the Ottoman period, when many Albanians, including those in Kosovo, converted to Islam. The motives and processes behind this conversion are complex and varied, including socio-political, economic factors, and individual choice (Endresen, 2011).

This period also marked the solidification of Albanian ethnic identity, as religious conversion often led to increased social mobility within the Ottoman system.

In contrast to Bosnian Muslims, or Bosniaks, who are Slavic Muslims, Kosovar Albanians maintain a strong connection to the Albanian national identity, even as they share the Islamic faith. The Albanian language, rather than religion, has been the primary marker of national identity for Kosovar Albanians, who see themselves as part of the larger Albanian nation, spread across Albania, Kosovo, and parts of Macedonia, Montenegro, and Serbia (Duijzings, 2000).

The identity of Kosovo Muslims or Kosovar Albanians is predominantly tied to their Albanian ethnic heritage and language, with religion being an important, but secondary, component of their identity. Undoubtedly, Kosovars are considered as white in the European census social construct (Duijzings, 2000).

Tertiary Model: Intersection of Race

Palestine: NATO's involvement in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is markedly different due to its sensitive geopolitical context. NATO does not have a direct role in the conflict and has not intervened to protect Palestinian Muslims, unlike in Bosnia or Kosovo. However, it has played a peripheral role through its Mediterranean Dialogue initiative, which seeks to promote regional security and stability and includes Israel and several Arab countries as partners (NATO, 2021).

NATO's role in protecting Muslim populations has been significant in Bosnia and Kosovo, but absent in Palestine. This divergence reflects the complex geopolitical

and legal factors that determine the nature and scope of NATO's interventions.

Palestinians are primarily of Arab descent, representing a diverse mix of racial backgrounds due to the region's rich history as a crossroads of various civilizations over the centuries. In the EU, the Arabs are non-white, as they are in the United States. The Arab identity of Palestinians is primarily linguistic and cultural rather than racial. The West does not recognize this fact. The biological distinction of color in the West determines the social construct one belongs to (Khalidi, 1997, Kendi, 2020). The majority of Palestinians would fall within what Western categorizations define as 'white', but this is an overly simplistic label that does not fully capture their ethnic diversity (Khalidi, 1997).

Historically, Palestinians have experienced profound struggles in defending their rights and homeland. The root of the contemporary Israeli-Palestinian conflict lies in the Zionist movement's goal of creating a Jewish state in Palestine and the subsequent establishment of Israel in 1948. This led to the displacement of approximately 700,000 Palestinians, known as the Nakba or "catastrophe" in Arabic (Morris, 2004).

Since 1967, Israel has maintained a military occupation of the West Bank and Gaza Strip, which has significantly affected Palestinian human rights. Practices such as the construction of Israeli settlements, home demolitions, restrictions on movement, and the use of administrative detention have been criticized as violating international law (HRW, 2020).

Palestinians have attempted to resist this situation through various means, including armed resistance, peaceful protests, diplomatic efforts, and international

advocacy. However, these efforts have been stymied by political fragmentation among Palestinians, power imbalances between Israel and Palestine, and the complex geopolitics of the Middle East (Beinin & Hajjar, 2005).

Accusations of racism in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict continue. Critics argue that Israeli laws and practices, such as the 2018 Nation-State Law which asserts the right of national self-determination in Israel is "unique to the Jewish people," institutionalize discrimination against Palestinians (HRW, 2020). However, these views are contested, with defenders arguing that Israel is a democratic state upholding the right to self-determination for the Jewish people. Using the matrix of cognitive dissonance, it is clear that the NATO, specifically the United States, the UK, and Canada, supports Israel in more ways than one. Meanwhile, Palestine, a non white state, is left to its own devices to protect itself against not only invasion but also racial cleansing.

The pattern of favoritism that the West has displayed in protecting Muslim nations in Europe seemingly indicates an inclination to prioritize the safety of those communities, which are primarily white, without second thoughts or remorse. However, when the same level of support, or potentially more, is urgently required in Palestine, the investment from the West appears to be minimal or even non-existent. In this context, the engagement and assistance of the United Nations become a sine qua non, a necessity without which Palestinian success cannot be achieved.

In sum, the West has a long-standing history of racial prejudice. Specifically, nations with a colonial past like the United Kingdom, the United States, and Canada, often employ

racial parameters in their approach to human rights. It's not enough to merely highlight the egregious wrongs; as Nikole Hannah-Jones states, "we must right the wrongs" (The 1619 Project, 2020). Bosnian, Kosovar, and Palestinian individuals are first and foremost human beings, irrespective of their religious beliefs. The level of support that the West extends to Bosnia and Kosovo must be matched, if not exceeded, in Palestine. We must eschew societal constructs that use race as a yardstick to measure our collective humanity. If we fail to treat each other as equals, most urgently as fellow humans, we risk regression and stagnation. Lastly, for those who enjoy stating that we always pin societal problems to be about race, it is crucial to say this: "When was it ever not about race?":

References:

- Ball, P., Betts, W., Scheuren, F., Dudukovich, J., & Asher, J. (2002). Killings and Refugee Flow in Kosovo March – June 1999. American Association for the Advancement of Science and the American Bar Association Central and East European Law Initiative.
- Bassiouni, M. C. (1994). Final report of the United Nations Commission of Experts established pursuant to security council resolution 780. United Nations.
- Beinin, J., & Hajjar, L. (2005). Palestine, Israel and the Arab-Israeli Conflict: A Primer. Middle East Research and Information Project (MERIP).
- Bougarel, X., Helms, E., & Duijzings, G. (2007). The New Bosnian Mosaic: Identities, Memories and Moral Claims in a Post-War Society. Ashgate.
- Bougarel, X. (2007). Islam and Politics in the Post-Communist Balkans. In N. Clayer & E. Germain (Eds.), *Islam in Inter-War Europe*. Columbia University Press.
- Ćirković, S. (2004). *The Serbs*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Donia, R. J., & Fine, J. V. A. (1994). *Bosnia and Hercegovina: A Tradition Betrayed*. Columbia University Press.
- Duijzings, G. (2000). *Religion and the Politics of Identity in Kosovo*. Hurst & Company.
- Emmert, T.A. (1990). *Kosovo: Legacy of a Medieval Battle*. Minnesota Mediterranean and East European Monographs.
- Endresen, C. (2011). The Nation and its 'New' Religion. The Case of Islam and Albanians. *Nationalities Papers*, 39(5), 647-661.
- Endresen, C. (2011). The Nation and the Nun: Mother Teresa, Albania's Muslim Majority and the Secular West. *Anthropology Today*, 27(1), 20-23.
- Fine, J. (1994). *The Late Medieval Balkans: A Critical Survey from the Late Twelfth Century to the Ottoman Conquest*. University of Michigan Press.
- Gallagher, T. (2005). *The Balkans in the New Millennium: In the Shadow of War and Peace*. Routledge.
- Hannah-Jones, N. (Ed.). (2020). *The 1619 Project*. The New York Times.
- HRW. (2020). *Born Without Civil Rights: Israel's Use of Draconian Military Orders to Repress Palestinians in the West Bank*. Human Rights Watch.

Independent International Commission on Kosovo. (2000). The Kosovo Report. Oxford University Press.

Inalcik, H. (1973). The Ottoman Empire: The Classical Age 1300-1600. Phoenix Press.

Jelavich, B. (1983). History of the Balkans: Eighteenth and Nineteenth Centuries. Cambridge University Press.

Judah, T. (2002). Kosovo: War and Revenge. Yale University Press.

Kendi, I. X. (2020). How to Be an Antiracist. Random House.

Khalidi, R. (1997). Palestinian Identity: The Construction of Modern National Consciousness. Columbia University Press.

Malcolm, N. (1998). Kosovo: A Short History. Macmillan.

Morris, B. (2004). The Birth of the Palestinian Refugee Problem Revisited. Cambridge University Press.

NATO. (2021). KFOR (Kosovo Force). https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_48818

NATO. (2021). Relations with Israel. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_50090.htm

Pavlowitch, S.K. (2002). Serbia: The History of an Idea. New York University Press.

Perritt, H.H. (2008). Kosovo Liberation Army: The Inside Story of an Insurgency. University of Illinois Press.

Pinson, M. (1994). The Muslims of Bosnia-Herzegovina, Their Historic Development from the Middle Ages to the Dissolution of Yugoslavia. Harvard University Press.

Ripley, T. (1999). Operation Deliberate Force: The UN and NATO campaign in Bosnia 1995. Centre for Defence and International Security Studies.

Sedlar, J.W. (1994). East Central Europe in the Middle Ages, 1000-1500. University of Washington Press.

Sicker, M. (2001). The Islamic World in Ascendancy: From the Arab Conquests to the Siege of Vienna. Praeger.

United Nations. (1995). The Fall of Srebrenica (A/54/549). Report of the Secretary-General pursuant to General Assembly resolution 53/35.

Funded by:

The University of York,
Heslington, York YO10 5DD,
United Kingdom,

The University of Pristina
Filipa Visnjica bb, 38220
Kosovska Mitrovica, Kosovo

Publication by:

Al Najah National University
الوطنية النجاح جامعة
Ramallah, Almasyoum,
Adel Almasri Bldg., 1st fl.

Written by:

Ivan Nikolic, Ph.D.
Florida University Systems
Copyright © 2023 Dr. Ivan Nikolic.
//43784637//34367862